

THE INTERPRETATION OF A REASONABLE ATTITUDE TO NATURE IN THE BOOK OF AVESTO AS PRINCIPAL NOBLE IDEAS.

Khaydarov Zakhridinbobir Umarovich
Associate professor of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682155>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about all the complex of sciences, fields, laws, and moral and social norms necessary for the development and development of mankind in the book “Avesta”, which is the oldest and unique treasure of knowledge in the world.

Keywords: religion, family, culture, tradition, value, Zoroastrianism, education, idea, family relationship, socio-economic, science, factor, loyalty, hard work, patriotism, earth, fire, water, air .

Introduction. As it is known, due to our independence, there was an opportunity to study our centuries-old national values and to incorporate their reflections into the direction of spiritual and educational education of young people. The role of spiritual and religious values is also important in raising the young generation as a perfect person and possessor of high morals. One of them is “Avesta”, which has a history of 3000 years. Many scientific and literary articles have been written about the sacred book “Avesta”, which is considered one of the rare artistic-philosophical, moral-aesthetic monuments of our nation and the entire humanity, and researches are being conducted.

Main part. Avesta, the world's most ancient and unique treasure of knowledge, contains all the complex of sciences, fields, laws, moral and social norms necessary for the development of mankind. Also, in the work, the glorification of the ideas of “good thought”, “good word”, “good deed” on the basis of moral perfection, in the way of raising the “perfect human being” constitutes the essence of the spiritual and educational world of Zoroastrians. “Avesta”, which is considered the holy book of Zoroastrians, is not only a set of religious beliefs, but also a set of invaluable noble ideas that embody artistic-philosophical, natural, ecological, social-economic, political-legal, educational-ethical views. In Zoroastrian religion and its holy book “Avesta”, man is encouraged to protect nature.

In “Avesta”, earth, fire, water, and air, which are the material basis of the world, are consecrated. Not only polluting the air, but also burying the dead animals and human corpses in the ground, pouring them into water, and burning them in fire were considered a sin. In order not to poison the earth, water, and air, it was customary to bury the bodies of the deceased in special ceramic vessels. According to the Zoroastrian religion, people elevated the Sun to the level of a divine being. After all, faith in the Sun, in turn, gave birth to respect for fire. Therefore, the Sun is a symbol of purity and vitality, and fire is a symbol of cleanliness and tidiness. In the philosophy of Zoroastrianism, there is a deep meaning of a unique simile, an idea of an incomparable truth.[1]

“Avesta” is the oldest monument of the spirituality of the peoples of Central Asia that has reached us, and it embodies the important laws and rules of Zoroastrianism. This monument is an immortal work about the emergence of the earth, all its resources - gardens, mountains, reservoirs, seas, all animals and plants, their history and existence. At the same time, this work is a source of reflection about man and humanity, society in general. It contains effective teachings and useful advices that every person who reads it will get spiritual strength and

power. Enriches his thinking. The wisdoms in it apply to all people and help to distinguish between good and bad and draw conclusions from them. There are ideas such as management of social life, solving conflicts in it, and these ideas have not lost their importance even now. Analyzing this work, you will witness that more attention is paid to the problems of nature. Its main theme is the relationship between man and society. According to this doctrine, the connection between nature and society, humanity and nature is eternal, it is not transient. People ensure their existence only when they are in contact with nature. Uses treats. Because nature grows and develops a person, helps to perfect his mental activity. Man would not be able to live without air, sunlight, and water from nature. We perceive these processes as natural, but we do not pay serious attention to them. Let's say that nature is nurture. However, the thoughts of our ancestors about nature are so valuable that we are close to disaster as a result of not following them.

Looking at the attitude of people to nature in the 20th-21st centuries, we can see that the above ideas are becoming reality.[2] The reason is that some people are not interested in the unprecedented damage to nature. For example, did many people think about what is returned to the earth in return for the gas and oil extracted from the earth? Do you know what levels of gas and oil residues coming out of high-altitude pipelines and oil spills from ships colliding in the seas lead to the levels? Anyone who thinks about this cannot ignore the sacredness of the ancient source "Avesta". It is worth following his example in changing the attitude towards nature:

"O God who created the universe! O Truth!" Who is the fourth person who made the earth happier than anyone else?

Ahura Mazda replied:

- Hey Sipiitmon Zarathustra!

He is the One who planted the most wheat, hemp and fruit trees! He is the One who sent water on the dry land and plowed the watery land. Unfortunate is the land that has not been sown and plowed for a long time. He dreams of a plow. Such a land is a mature girl who has entered puberty. This girl is longing for a baby and a good pillow mate.

- Hey Sipiitmon Zarathustra!

Whoever plows the land with the left hand and the right hand, with the right hand and the left hand, the land will give him prosperity. She looks like a beautiful and pure girl. This girl enters her husband's house and gives birth to children in her bed to her honest partner. The earth also gives abundant fruits.[3]

At Avesto, nature protection is a top priority. Growing crops on the land, honoring the land, and taking care of it are repeatedly mentioned.

- Oh, the One who created the universe!

Oh, the truth!

Where is the first place in the world where the land is the happiest?

Ahura Mazda replied:

Oh Sipiitmon Zarathustra!

Such a place holds in its hands clean wood, barsam, mortar and fresh milk, firm in its faith in its faith, full of voice, delighted with the love of wide pastures, and it makes the pastures sing. an Ashavan is the trodden ground.

O God who created the universe!

O truth!

Where is the second happiest place in the world?

Ahura Mazda replied:

- Such a place is a place where an Ashavan built a house. In that house there is a good life. A herd of cows and a housewife, children and flocks live in this house: A herd of cows is well cared for. Ashavan will be magic .

The food of the dogs is good, and the sustenance of the good dogs is plentiful. The housewife is happy, the children are happy. The fire is always roaring. Every beautiful event of life leads to goodness. Such a place is the second happiest place in the world.

Thus, in “Avesta” the life activities of the earth, soil, plants, and animals are carefully described from the point of view of that time, and these descriptions have not lost their importance even now. How to take care of the land, establish irrigation works, turn the desert into a garden, preserve and breed livestock, especially the development of the sheep, camel, and goat breeding sectors of animal husbandry are important in preserving nature. significance is defined. It is said that if someone pays attention to the increase of livestock and the flowering of pastures, he will be honored by Ahura Mazda. It says that it is the duty of every person to respect the animals that ensure the unity of nature. In addition, it was necessary to plant fruit trees on the banks of drinking water sources.

Violators of environmental laws, including the owner of the house who piled garbage near the street door, were given 25 lashes, and the person who took water from a pond or spring in an unclean container was given 5 lashes. Large fines were imposed on those who pollute wells and ponds.[4]

Our ancestors fought tooth and nail against the destruction of nature. In “Avesta”, the following points are stated about cleanliness, clothing, bed, dirt that has touched a dead body, cleaning water and dishes that have been touched by a dead dog:

- O God who created the universe! O Truth!

If the dishes used by people touch the corpses of dogs or people, can they be purified?

Ahura Mazda replied:

It can be cleaned.

How can it be purified?

If the vessel is made of gold, it is washed once with silver, once covered with soil, and once with water. Then it will be pure. If the vessel is made of wire, it is washed twice with sand, twice covered with soil, and twice rinsed with water. This will make the dish clean.[5] If the vessel is made of tin, it is washed three times with sand, three times covered with soil, and three times rinsed with water. In this way, the vessel is cleaned. If the vessel is made of iron, it is washed four times with sand, four times with earth, and six times with water. In this way, the dish will be clean.

Conclusion. It can be concluded that it is alien in nature! there is no thing itself. They are connected with each other, and people only need to put them in their place. Thus, the historical significance of “Avesta” is that it reflects the attitude of our ancestors to nature, in general, to all the goodness and goodness in the world. Along with thoughts about the historical development of man, the future and vital activities of man are explained in connection with nature. Noble ideas such as the need to respect nature, the rational use of natural resources, and the prevention of wastage were praised.

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